

Synthesis of ionic chelates of hafnium(IV)-uracil complexes

Ekta Malhotra^a, N. K. Kaushik^{a*} and Gurdinder Singh Sodhi^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Delhi University, Delhi-110 007, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, S. G. T. B. Khalsa College (University of Delhi), Delhi-110 007, India

Manuscript received 13 July 2001, accepted 5 April 2002

Ionic chelate complexes of uracil and hafnium(IV) the type $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+\text{X}^-$ [HL = uracil; X = CuCl₃, ZnCl₃, CdCl₃, HgCl₃, C₆H₅NHNHCS₂] have been synthesized. The compounds are 1 : 1 electrolytes. Various thermodynamical parameters have been calculated and the variation of activation energy has been correlated with the nature of metal ion in the anionic moiety. The complexes have been evaluated for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Uracil is a constituent of nucleic acids. This biomolecule possesses a number of bonding sites and thus forms a number of stable metal complexes¹. Moreover, pyrimidine analogs are also associated with diverse biological activities². Our interest in the investigation of the bonding mode and biological activity of the pyrimidine based ligands prompted us to synthesize, characterize and study the activity of a number of ionic chelates of the type $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+\text{X}^-$ [HL = uracil; X = CuCl₃, ZnCl₃, CdCl₃, HgCl₃, C₆H₅NHNHCS₂].

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are light brown in colour. The conductance (in nitrobenzene) data indicate that these complexes were 1 : 1 electrolytes.

The complexing sites of uracil may be determined by the interpretation of 1500–1800 cm⁻¹ region of the IR spectra. Susi and Ard³ reported that the bands in this region may be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}(2)=\text{O})$, in-plane $\nu(\text{C}(4)=\text{O}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and out-of-plane $\nu(\text{C}(4)=\text{O})$. It has also been ob-

served that due to the participation of carbonyl groups in complexation the bands in the 1500–1800 cm⁻¹ region shifted to a lower frequency⁴. Moreover, it has been reported that the carbonyl at C(4) has a greater affinity to get coordinated to the metal ion^{1,5}. The uracil spectrum showed a doublet peaked at 1710 and 1695 cm⁻¹. In the metal complexes, the former band shifted to ca. 1670 cm⁻¹, whereas the latter absorbed at ca. 1600 cm⁻¹. In the complexes, the hafnium(IV) ion displaced the proton at N(3), similar to the complexes reported earlier⁶ and consequently the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ stretching frequency was also perturbed. It shifted from 1390 in the ligand to ca. 1350 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. Thus, the uracil moiety acted as a bidentate group, being chelated to the Hf^{IV} ion through carbonyl at C(4) and deprotonated N(3).

The uracil ligand showed two absorption bands at 260 (log ϵ 4.0) and 220 nm (log ϵ 1.5). The former was attributed to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the carbonyl group, while the latter to the corresponding transition of the N \cdots C \cdots O

Table 1. Physical and thermal data of the uracil complexes*

Compd.	Dec. temp. °C	Λ^a	Thermogravimetry				Differential thermal analysis		
			Temp. range K	<i>n</i>	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$S^{\#}$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Therm. eff.	T_{max} K	ΔH Jg ⁻¹
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+ [\text{CuCl}_3]^-$	145	29.4	418–787	1	10.41	0.487	Exo.	599	65.01
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+ [\text{ZnCl}_3]^-$	187	26.5	460–796	1	12.60	1.411	Exo.	737	110.62
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+ [\text{CdCl}_3]^-$	200	28.3	473–840	1	15.31	2.560	Exo.	776	136.99
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+ [\text{HgCl}_3]^-$	155	26.8	428–773	1	19.13	4.332	Exo.	719	442.25
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+ [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHNHCS}_2]^-$	175	25.2	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

* All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

^a In $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$; $c = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$.

chromophore⁷. On complexation the absorption due to the carbonyl group shifted to *ca.* 270 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 5.2), indicating the involvement of carbonyl oxygen in complexation. The N \cdots C \cdots O chromophore in the metal complexes absorbed at *ca.* 226 nm ($\log \epsilon$ *ca.* 4.5).

The ¹H NMR signal of uracil⁸ appeared at δ 6.37 (1H, d, H(5), *J* 6.0 Hz) and 7.95 (1H, d, H(6), *J* 6.0 Hz), which remained unaffected on complexation. The cyclopentadienyl group showed signal at δ 6.9–7.0 (m, 10H) in the metal complexes.

The ¹³C NMR spectrum of free uracil⁹ showed resonance signals at 110.9 (C(2)), 123.8 (C(4)), 59.8 ppm (C(5)) and 101.6 (C(6)). In the metal complexes, the signal due to C(4) shifted to *ca.* 132.8 ppm. The downfield shift, on complexation, was attributed to the involvement of C(4) carbonyl in complexation. The signal due to C(2) was observed at *ca.* 111.8 ppm in the metal complexes. In the metal complexes, a signal appeared at *ca.* 122.2 ppm due to carbons of the cyclopentadienyl rings¹⁰. In case of the complexes containing anionic phenyldithiocarbazate moiety, the following signals were observed : 153.0 C(1), 112.1 (C(2,6)), 130.1 (C(3,5)) and 119.2 ppm (C(4)), while the signal due to CS₂ carbon appeared at *ca.* 169.0 ppm.

Thermal studies :

The thermal data are shown in Table 1. The complexes finally decompose to the oxides of hafnium and the metal in the anionic moiety. In case of the complex containing mercury in the anionic moiety, the observed weight-loss corresponds to the formation of HfO₂ only, since HgO volatilizes at such high temperatures. The order of the reaction (*n*) and the activation energy (*E_a*) of the thermal decomposition reaction have been elucidated by the method of Coats and Redfern¹¹. The entropy of activation (*S[‡]*) has been calculated by the method of Zsako¹².

The order of thermal decomposition reaction in all the complexes is found to be one. A comparison of the activation energy of complexes reveals that the *E_a* values follow the order : $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+[\text{CuCl}_3]^- < [(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+ < [\text{ZnCl}_3]^- < [(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+[\text{CdCl}_3]^- < [(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+[\text{HgCl}_3]^-$. This may be explained on the basis of the fact that larger cations are stabilized by larger anions. The complex cation $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+$ is very large in size and the size of the M(II) ions in the anionic moiety varies in the order : Cu^{II} < Zn^{II} < Cd^{II} < Hg^{II}. In case of the complex $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+[\text{HgCl}_3]^-$, the large size of Hg^{II} ion in the anionic moiety, helps in effective stabilization of the complex cation and therefore gives rise to a higher lattice energy. This makes thermal degradation of the complex rela-

tively difficult and thus, the reaction involves a higher value of *E_a*. For the complex $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$, the small size of the Cu^{II} ion in the anionic moiety leads to a relatively poor stabilization of the complex cation and to a comparatively lower lattice energy. Thus the thermal decomposition reaction involves a lower value of *E_a*.

It is, therefore, evident that the nature of metal ion in the anionic moiety contributes to the variation in the activation energy for the thermal degradation of the complexes. The energy of activation, in turn, reflects the kinetic lability of the complexes. The compounds with lower *E_a* values are more labile as compared to those with higher *E_a* values.

The apparent activation entropy has a positive value for all the complexes. Within a given series, the complex containing Cu^{II} ion in the anionic moiety has the lowest value of *S[‡]*, while the one containing Hg^{II} ion has the highest. Hence, the former decomposes with lowest degree of randomness, while the latter with greatest.

The TG data of the complexes are supplemented by DTA studies. The heat of reaction (ΔH) for the thermal decomposition reaction has been enumerated from the DTA curves¹³. The temperature-dependent calibration coefficient has been obtained from the Currell equation¹⁴.

Bactericidal and fungicidal activities :

The complexes containing Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} ions in the anionic moiety have been screened for antibacterial activity against pathogenic strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Zymomonas mobilis* using uracil ligand as the standard and at concentrations 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in DMF. The inhibitory power of the complexes was greater than the control. In general, it was observed that the complexes containing mercury in the anionic moiety were more active than those containing copper. Moreover, the complexes were observed to be more active against *P. aeruginosa* and *Z. mobilis* compared to *E. coli*.

The antifungal activity data revealed that (i) complexes containing phenyldithiocarbazate group in the anionic moiety possessed stronger antifungal activity than those containing mercury in the anionic moiety and (ii) the former complexes showed greater inhibition at lower concentrations than the latter.

Experimental

Instruments : Elico CM-180 conductivity bridge; Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 2000 spectrophotometer for IR spectra; Beckman DU-64 spectrophotometer for UV spectra; Bruker Spectrospin advance 300 spectrometer for ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra; Rigaku Thermoflex PTC-10A in-

strument for simultaneous recording of TG-DTA curves in air at a heating rate of $10^{\circ} \text{ min}^{-1}$. For TG, the instrument was calibrated using calcium oxalate while for DTA, calibration was done using Indium metal. A flat bed type Al-crucible was used with α -alumina (99% pure) as the reference material for DTA. Uracil (Aldrich) and hafnocene dichloride, $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfCl}_2$ (Alfa) were used as such.

*Potassium phenyldithiocarbazate*¹⁵ : To a stirred ice-cold solutions of phenylhydrazine (0.05 mol) and KOH (0.050 mol) in a minimum quantity of alcohol, was added CS_2 (0.050 mol) dropwise with stirring. The temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at $0\text{--}5^{\circ}$ and the stirring continued for another 1 h. Then a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (50 ml; 1 : 1, v/v) was added to it and the resulting solid was washed with ether and dried.

$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}]^+X^-$ ($X = \text{CuCl}_3, \text{ZnCl}_3, \text{CdCl}_3, \text{HgCl}_3$) : A solution of the metal salt $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ZnCl_2 , CdCl_2 or HgCl_2 (0.25 mmol) in acetone (10 ml) was added to a stirred solution of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) dichloride (0.25 mmol) and uracil (HL) (0.25 mmol) in acetone (20 ml). The contents were stirred for 8 h and filtered. The filtrate was reduced to one-fourth of its original volume followed by the addition of petroleum ether. The resulting complexes were filtered, dried and crystallized from acetone by the addition of a few drops of petroleum ether.

$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfL}][\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHNHCS}_2]^-$: A mixture of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) dichloride (0.25 mmol) and uracil (HL) (0.25 mmol) was stirred for 8 h in water (10 ml) followed by addition of potassium phenyldithiocarbazate (0.25 mmol) in a minimum quantity of water. The contents were stirred till precipitation was complete. The

solid product was filtered, dried and crystallized from acetone-petroleum ether.

References

1. S. Mansy and R. Tobias. *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 287.
2. J. R. J. Sorenson, R. E. Stull, K. Ramakrishna, B. L. Johnson, E. Riddell, D. F. Ring, T. M. Rolniak and D. L. Stewart in "Trace Substances in Environmental Health-XIV-a Symposium", ed. D. D. Hemphill, University of Missouri, Columbia, 1980, p. 252; A. Grollman and E. F. Grollman, "Pharmacology and Therapeutics", 7th. ed., Lea and Febiger, Philadelphia, 1970.
3. H. Susi and J. S. Ard. *Spectrochim. Acta. Part A*, 1971, **27**, 1549.
4. M. Goodgame and K. W. Johns. *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1680.
5. J. A. Carrabine and M. Sundaralingam, *Biochemistry*, 1971, **10**, 292.
6. Y. L. Tan and A. Beck, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1973, **299**, 500; S. Mansy, T. E. Wood, J. C. Sprowles and R. S. Tobias, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **152**, 67.
7. W. Jiazhu, H. Jingshuo, H. Liyiao, S. Dashuang and H. Shengzhi, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **152**, 67.
8. J. Zemlčeka and J. P. Horwitz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 4089.
9. P. D. Ellis, R. B. Dunlap, A. L. Pollard, K. Seidman and A. D. Cardin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 4398.
10. K. Sambhy, J. Kaur, G. Singh and G. S. Sodhi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 355.
11. A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature (London)*, 1964, **68**, 201.
12. J. Zsakó. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 2406.
13. W. E. Collins in "Analytical Calorimetry", eds. R. S. Porter and J. M. Johnson, Plenum, New York, 1970, Vol. 2, p. 353.
14. B. R. Curell in "Thermal Analysis", eds. R. F. Schwenker and P. D. Garn, Academic, New York, 1969, Vol. 2, p. 1185.
15. S. Bhatia, N. K. Kaushik and G. S. Sodhi. *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **127**, 141.